

Observations on the Mannich Reaction of Estrone¹

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A route to 2,4-dimethylestradiol by the Mannich reaction is described. 2-Aziridino methylestrone and 2-(2,2'-dichloroethylamino)methyl estrone have been prepared.

The introduction of so-called alkylating groupings, that is, 2,2'-dichloroethylamino or aziridino residues, into aromatic steroids by the Mannich reaction was investigated in this laboratory but was not published because of Patton's papers² on this subject. In view of the recent report by Vaughan *et al.*³ on the preparation of alkylating agents from lawsone we wish, however, to describe the introduction of alkylating groupings into estrone by the Mannich reaction.

An excess over the theoretical amounts of the reagents is necessary to induce the reaction when estrone is heated with formaldehyde and aziridine or diethanolamine in ethanolic solution. In the reaction with aziridine, disappearance of the phenolic hydroxyl band in the infrared spectrum of the crude reaction product suggests hydrogen bonding as observed also by Patton². The aziridine derivative, though isolated in the solid form, could not be recrystallised due to its decomposition in the process to estrone. The diethanolamine derivative, however, is reasonably stable and recrystallisation allows its isolation in a crystalline form.

Patton has shown that the Mannich reaction with estrone or estradiol takes place exclusively in 2-position of the molecule. Substitution in 4-position, however, may be obtained when 2-methylestradiol is allowed to react with formaldehyde and diethylamine. The product could only be isolated as a resin, but when reduced with Raney nickel, 2,4-dimethylestradiol could be obtained pure in crystalline form. It is interesting that 2,4-dimethylestradiol is devoid of estrogenic action when tested as usual, whereas 2-(2,2'-diethanolamino)methyl estrone shows low activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Aziridinomethyl Estrone.—Aziridine (0.4 ml) and 38% formaldehyde solution (0.8 ml) were added to a solution of estrone in absolute ethanol (1.01g in 12 ml) and heated under reflux. After 4 hours there was still undissolved estrone present and more absolute ethanol (2ml) was added and heating to complete solution continued for 2 more hours. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature and then filtered under stirring

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2. Patton, *Chem. Ind.*, 1959, 923; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 2149; 1961, 26, 1677.

into filtered ice water. The white precipitate was held in the cold room for several hours, filtered, washed thoroughly with water, and finally dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} . It was obtained as a fine white powder in 1.25 g. yield; m.p. 145-48°. It is easily soluble in alcohols and in benzene from which it is precipitated with pentane. $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 134^\circ$ (chloroform) λ_{max}^{KBr} : 1720 cm^{-1} (17-keto), 885 cm^{-1} (1,2,4,5 aromatic substitution). Found: C, 75.95; H, 8.21; N, 4.34. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{27}O_2N\frac{1}{2}H_2O$: C, 75.40; H, 7.93; N, 4.19%.

2-(2,2'-Diethanolamino)methyl Estrone.—2,2'-Diethanolamine (3.92 g.) and 38% formaldehyde solution (1.6 ml) were added to estrone (1.01g.) in abs. ethanol⁴ (25 ml.). While this mixture was refluxed, the estrone went slowly into solution; heating was continued for 20 hours. The solution was then diluted with benzene and ether, shaken, and washed thoroughly with water. Removal of the solvents after drying with anhydrous sodium sulphate gave a gum which was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol or benzene-hexane in fine needles, m.p. 135-136°; yield 0.960 g. $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 123^\circ$ (chloroform). λ_{max}^{KBr} : 890 cm^{-1} . (1,2,4,5 aromatic substitution). (Found: C, 71.29; H, 8.61; N, 3.59. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{33}O_4N$: C, 71.28; H, 8.58; N, 3.61%.)

2-(2,2'-Dichloroethylamino)methyl Estrone.—The foregoing compound (3.87g., 0.01 M) was dissolved in chloroform (50 ml) and added over a period of 1½ hours to a solution of thionyl chloride (3.5g. 0.03 M) in chloroform (20 ml) which was cooled in an ice bath. At the end the mixture turned violet in colour and an oil separated. Stirring was continued at 15-25° for 3 hrs. and then overnight at room temperature. Removal of the solvent afforded a dark violet residue, which was dissolved in absolute ethanol (125 ml) and treated with charcoal. The volume was then reduced to 75 ml. under vacuum and ether added until the solution became turbid. The solid was filtered and dried in vacuum after washing with ether; yield 2.9 g., m.p. 194-98°. This hydrochloride was finely powdered and stirred vigorously for 30 minutes with saturated aqueous solution of potassium carbonate (50 ml). The mixture was shaken with benzene and the solution washed twice with water. After drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, removal of the solvent in vacuum gave a crystalline residue, which was recrystallised from acetone (with charcoal treatment) as fine needles m.p. 172-176° yield 1.6 g., $[\alpha]_D^{20} = 112^\circ$ (chloroform): λ_{max}^{KBr} : 680 cm^{-1} (C-Cl) and 885 cm^{-1} . (1,2,4,5 aromatic substitution). Found: C, 65.29; H, 7.31; N, 3.44; Cl, 16.67. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{31}O_2NCl_2$: C, 65.08; H, 7.36; N, 3.29; Cl, 16.74%.

2,4-Dimethylestradiol.—2-Methylestradiol (2.1g.) prepared according to Patton² was refluxed with diethylamine (7.5 ml) in ethanol (37 ml) and benzene (22 ml) and in the course of one hour two portions of 38% formaldehyde solution (2.5 ml) were added. Heating was continued for 18 hours and then the solvents were removed under vacuum. The residue was a gum which resisted crystallisation. It was dissolved in ethanol (300 ml) and refluxed with Raney nickel (25 g.) for 24 hours. After removal of the catalyst and evaporation of solvent, the gummy residue solidified when treated with aqueous ethanol and recrystallised from this solvent, yield, 1.2. g., m.p. 214-8°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 63^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). λ_{max}^{KBr} : 3200-3400 cm^{-1} . (C-3 OH and C-17 OH) 820 cm^{-1} . (1,2,3,4,5 aromatic substitution). The NMR spectrum shows the presence of three isolated CH_3 groups, peaks at τ 7.763 (2-methyl),

3. Vaughan *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 2992.

4. Dr. Patton kindly made his directions for the Mannich reaction available to us before publication, but in our work the addition of benzene had no advantage.

7.877 (4-methyl), 9.238 (18-methyl) and 3.042 (aromat. = $\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{H}$). (Found: C, 79.91; H, 9.45. Calc. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$: C, 79.95; H, 9.38%.)

2,4-Dimethyl-17-acetoxyestradiol.—A mixture of 2,4-dimethylestradiol (350 mg) with 17.5 ml of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 4½ hours when a solution was obtained which was poured into a mixture of ice and saturated sodium chloride solution. After keeping for several hours in the cold room the fine white precipitate formed was filtered and washed well with water. It was dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum, yield was 350 mg. Repeated recrystallization from dilute methanol gave needles, m.p. 177-80°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 41^\circ$, (chloroform). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3600 (C-3 OH), 1725 cm^{-1} . (acetate CO), 1275 cm^{-1} . (acetate), 835 cm^{-1} . (1,2,3,4,5 aromatic substitution). (Found: C, 77.07; H, 8.87. Calc. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_3$: C, 77.15; H, 8.83%.)

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